

Studies on the Effect of Temperature and pH on the Gelation of Silicic Acid

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The effect of variation of temperature and of pH on the condensation polymerisation of silicic acid, prepared by ion-exchange method, have been studied separately. The Arrhenius equation for determination of the activation energy has been employed and the values of E obtained are 10,000 calories, when water is the dispersion medium, and 9,000 calories, when mixtures of water and ethanol and water and glycol are the media. The maximum time of gelation of a particular silicic acid sol is at a pH equal to that of a pure acid (where no extra amount of strong acid or base has been added). This pH lies between 2 and 3, depending on the concentration of SiO_2 in the sol. On either side of this pH, the time required for gelation is reduced due to catalytic action of H^+ or OH^- ions.

The effect of pH and of temperature on the gelation of silicic acid, prepared by using sodium silicate and an acid, have been investigated by various workers¹⁻⁹. As the sols used by previous workers contained a considerable amount of electrolytes as impurity^{10,11}, it has been thought desirable to investigate the subject by using a pure sample of silicic acid sol, obtained by ion-exchange method¹², described previously.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sodium metasilicate used was of A.R. quality of E. Merck. A strong cation-exchange resin, Amberlite-IR-120(H), analytical grade of Rohm and Haas Company, Pennsylvania, was used. Ethanol, ethylene glycol, HCl, H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 , acetic acid, and ammonia used were all of A.R. quality. Silicic acid was prepared and estimated by the same method as described earlier¹². A Cambridge Bench type pH-meter was used for the measurement of pH.

Determination of Gel Point.—The determination of the exact gel point was made by the floating ball method¹², described in a previous communication.

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Effect of Temperature

Silicic acid of three different concentrations were used and in each case experiments were performed at four different temperatures. The dispersion media used were water, a mixture of water and ethanol, and a mixture of water and glycol. As soon as the silicic acid was prepared, four samples of it were placed in four baths, maintained at different temperatures, and the time of gelation was determined by the floating ball method¹². In all the cases, especially where water-ethanol was the medium or working at high temperatures, care was taken for the loss of solvent by evaporation due to frequent opening of the cork for noting the gel point. This was avoided by working with three test tubes containing the same sol-solvent mixture, two of them being occasionally tested and the third one tested at the proper time (the idea of the proper time can be gathered from the first two trial experiments). Having thus known the time of gelation, t , at different temperatures, $\log t$ was plotted against $1/T$. A straight line was obtained from the slope of which the value of the activation energy was calculated. The plots are shown in Fig. 1 (curves 1-6).

FIG. 1

Effect of pH

The pH of the pure silicic acid sol was varied to lower values by addition of acids and to higher values by addition of a base. The acids were HCl, H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄, and acetic acid and the base used was NH₄OH. The required amount of an acid or the base was added to the silicic acid, just after its preparation, in different test tubes of the same diameter. The pH of the solution in each of the test tubes was measured by using the pH-meter and the solutions were kept undisturbed at a constant temperature in a bath. The time of gelation was noted by the floating ball method¹². The starting time was noted just when the acid and the base had been added to the silicic acid. A plot of the setting time against pH is shown in Fig. 2.

DISCUSSION

The silicic acid, prepared by the ion-exchange method, has been found to set after some time. In a recent communication¹², this process of setting has been attributed to the poly-

merisation of the monosilicic acid molecules through the agency of their hydroxyl groups (functional groups), analogous to the condensation polymerisation of glycol-adipic acid, observed by Ffory¹³. In the present system, the reaction has been found to be of the third order. This has been explained by the reaction between two hydroxyl groups from two silicic acid molecules, catalysed by a third hydroxyl group arising either from one of the reacting molecules or from a third molecule.

FIG. 2

The velocity constant of the gelation or condensation process may be considered to be inversely proportional to the time of gelation, t , and putting $k = K/t$, where K is a constant, the Arrhenius equation can be written as

$$\frac{d \ln t}{dT} = - \frac{E}{RT^2}$$

or

$$\log t = \frac{E}{2.303 RT} + \text{constant.}$$

It means that a plot of $\log t$ against $1/T$ will be linear, the slope of which will determine the activation energy, E . Such a relationship has actually been obtained in the present case, justifying the use of the Arrhenius equation (vide Fig. 1). From the slopes of the graph, the activation energy has been calculated and found to be 10,000 calories in the pH range of 2.26 to 2.54 in water and about 9,000 calories in the pH range of 2.30 to 2.50 in water-ethanol and water-glycol media. The value of the activation energy, obtained by Hurd *et al.*¹⁷ is about 11,000 calories in the pH range of + 0.5 to -0.5, which is fairly close to that found by us only in the aqueous medium.

It appears from what has been demonstrated in the curves of Fig. 2 that the maximum time of gelation always corresponds to the pH of the pure acid. As the pH of the silicic acid is decreased or increased by addition of an acid or a base respectively, the time of gelation decreases. This may be attributed to the catalytic acceleration of the rate of condensation of the OH⁻ groups by H⁺ ions, when an acid is added, and by OH⁻ ions, when a base is added. Observations of different workers on the effect of pH on the rate of gelation

do not agree with one another. Working with a pure silicic acid, we have obtained a pH range of 2 to 3, depending on the concentration of SiO_2 , in which the rate is the slowest. This is in accordance with the observations of some of the previous authors^{2,3} and constitutes a confirmation of their works.

The authors express their grateful thanks to the authorities of the Burmah Oil Company for financial aid.

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Received May 6, 1963.